

SPIRITUALITY IS A GUARANTEE OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

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"For us, spirituality is mutual trust between people, respect and attention, building the future of the nation and the state together is a complex of noble aspirations and exemplary qualities".

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Annotation. In this article, harmonizing the interests of different nationalities and ensuring harmony among them is considered one of the decisive factors of development in our country. There is an opinion that great importance will be attached to the implementation of this idea in our country

Key words: spirituality, culture, enlightenment, society, social, human, spiritual value, tradition, tradition, idea, purpose. ethics, religion and education.

In today's world, there are many universal values that are equally important for all mankind and all nations. Spirituality has a special place among them.

Spirituality and enlightenment, education and upbringing are an integral part of human life, and the society, goodness, spiritual world, the meaning of life in general, developed by them cannot be imagined. Therefore, in the humanistic society, great attention has always been paid to spirituality and enlightenment, education and training.

According to experts, there are about three thousand nationalities on Earth, which unite 96% of humanity. The remaining 4 percent are ethnic groups and tribes. Of all the nations in the world, only about 200 have their own statehood. In such conditions, it is necessary to regularly study the interests, mentality, and aspirations of nations all over the world, and to always take this into account in political and social life.

This issue is also very important for our country. Representatives of many nationalities and peoples have lived together in the territory of Uzbekistan since ancient times. Today, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples live in Uzbekistan. Every nation is a miracle of the Creator and has its own language, customs, values and traditions. Harmonizing the interests of different nationalities and ensuring harmony among them is one of the decisive factors of development in our country. Great importance is attached to the implementation of this idea in our country. As the first President of our country, I.A. Karimov, stated the unique policy of Uzbekistan in this regard, he noted: "The sacred duty of the Uzbek nation, which is the majority among the population of the republic, is not only to restore the mother tongue, its national culture and history, but also the fate of the few peoples who live together for, in order to preserve their unique cultural and spiritual characteristics, to be responsible for creating equal conditions and opportunities for them to mature and express their identity". This responsibility is the moral basis of mutual respect, friendship and solidarity between people of different nationalities and peoples living in the same society and working towards a common goal. The national idea, based on high

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VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

spiritual principles and a great sense of responsibility, creates conditions for the full realization of the talent and potential of the representative of each nation and mobilizes it towards noble goals such as the development of the Motherland, peace of the country, and the well-being of the people.

It is known that during the time of the former Union, the interests of the totalitarian regime were prioritized, and the person, his rights and interests, and his spiritual and spiritual life became secondary things. In particular, the concept of "Spirituality" lost its original meaning and significance and was condemned to oblivion. After all, spirituality is understood not as a phenomenon that makes a person - a person, a nation - a nation, defines their value and identity, and has been formed and developed as a whole system over the centuries, but some moral qualities, feelings and experiences specific to a person. Most social science majors were used to researching and promoting spirituality not as a separate and distinct phenomenon, but as simple moral concepts. However, it is a historical fact that with such a superficial approach, it is impossible to understand the phenomenon of spirituality, which has deep historical, theoretical and practical foundations, in its entire essence and scope, and to study it on a holistic and systematic basis.

After we gained independence, a person, his interests, rights and freedoms were declared as the highest value in our country. As much as the issue of building a new life and a new society has become an urgent and important task in Uzbekistan, it has become an urgent need to completely change the views on spirituality, to restore the age-old criteria demanded by the times, the original meaning and social significance of this unique phenomenon. Such wide-ranging issues were deeply substantiated theoretically and practically in the works of the first President of our country, Islam Karimov. Therefore, the years of independence were for us a period of spiritual renewal and growth, along with renewal and changes in all spheres of life.

^{book} "High spirituality is an insurmountable force" published in 2008 is of great importance in strengthening the scientific-theoretical foundations of our ideas and concepts about spirituality, updating views and conclusions in this regard, and raising it to a higher level. Because in this book, the phenomenon of spirituality is first of all deeply analyzed in connection with history and today, human, people, and nation categories, national and universal values, traditions, and social institutions, and its complete definition, system of concepts, and main principles were explained on a conceptual basis. Thanks to the deep opinions, methodological views, theoretical and practical conclusions in this work, we can see spirituality today as a unique phenomenon, unique to every nation in the world, which occupies an incomparable place in the life of mankind, opens up new opportunities depending on the requirements and criteria of the time, and becomes an insurmountable force. we imagine as a system. According to the definition given by our head of state, spirituality is an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification, spiritual growth, strengthens the inner world of a person, strengthens his will, makes his faith whole, awakens his conscience, and is the criterion of all his views.

During the former union, the issue of spirituality was neglected. At that time, not being able to interpret it as a holistic phenomenon did not allow to form a general idea about it. After our independence, attention to it increased, restoration and preservation of our spiritual values became a priority. In this regard, extensive practical and theoretical work has been carried out. In our country, in the field of spirituality, a new system has been formed that is compatible with

¹ Karimov I. A. Let us have a free and prosperous country. 2nd floor. -T., Uzbekistan, 1996. -155 p.

international standards, universal values and our national interests, instead of the highly ideological sciences of the former union.

In particular, the first leader of our independent country, Islam Karimov, in his work "High spirituality - indomitable power" ¹, the scientific and methodological foundations of the study of the phenomenon of spirituality are shown in detail, which is important in comprehensively solving the tasks in this regard. Thanks to this work, it became possible to deeply understand the true essence of spirituality, to study its specific features based on new conceptual approaches. As stated in this work, the concept of "spirituality" in our country fully embodies ideological, ideological, educational, cultural, religious and moral views in the life of society. Therefore, when thinking about this topic, all these views can be summarized and expressed through the concept of "Spirituality" in a broad sense.

Concepts of spirituality are directly related to education and upbringing. Education connects a person's life with science, education forms his conscience. Science gives satisfaction to man, and conscience is the jewel of his life. There is no humanity without it ¹. The main task of education is to teach humanity. The conclusion is that there is no education without education, no education without knowledge. Yes, the happiness and power of the nation depends on its enlightenment and freedom as well as its spirituality. The stronger the enlightenment, the greater the power, the higher the happiness. Because the humanitarian philosophy of education is necessary.

It is his spirituality that makes a man a man. Because thought and speech give birth to unlimited possibilities of using one's own experience.

It is known that the development of the society is connected with the economy, one without the other, they are two mutually inseparable spheres of life and development of the society. They do not negate each other, but strengthen each other, describe each other, develop and improve. "If economic growth and development are the body of society, then spirituality, enlightenment and maturity of political consciousness are its soul and soul" ².

It is known from history that in Western countries, including some countries that were formed in place of the former union, spirituality is not considered as a separate phenomenon. It is generally understood as a concept related to religion or morality. Sometimes these terms are equated with each other, and in some cases it is suggested that both of them can replace spirituality. In addition, there are also opinions that spirituality is a part of morality or religion, therefore, it can be understood as a set of characteristics that exist in these two values. Such approaches are one of the main reasons why spirituality has not become a separate science in these countries.

As stated in the work "High Spirituality - Invincible Power", "... while we are thinking about spirituality, we should analyze this issue thoroughly and deeply, not limiting ourselves only to its favorable and positive aspects, but also not to ignore such complex aspects." ¹. In this regard, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following aspects of spirituality:

- a set of requirements and rules that regulate social relations in society and interactions between people;
- system of spiritual values, customs and traditions, ideals, ideals and goals;

¹ Karimov I. A. Let us have a free and prosperous country. 2nd floor. -T., Uzbekistan, 1996. -155 p.

¹ Ganieva Gulirukhsora Islamovna. Education and training is a spiritual need, a social need. - Tashkent: Science and Technology Publishing House, 2010. - Page 16.

² Karimov I. A. Let us have a free and prosperous country. 2nd floor. -T., Uzbekistan, 1996. -266 p.

¹ Karimov I. A. High spirituality - Invincible power. -Tashkent: Spirituality, 2008. -140 p.

- a whole set of spiritual phenomena consisting of ethics, culture, enlightenment, religion and education system;
- spiritual processes, creative activity of a person improving himself and the world in which he lives and its results;
- human perfection, level of improvement of his spiritual image, set of personal - moral characteristics and educational qualities;
- moral requirements and principles interconnected with all spheres of society, as well as a system of criteria defining human life and activity.

Spirituality is based on the interaction of the following main aspects in the form of a set of human characteristics and qualities. First of all, it is not a gift of fate, it has matured as a result of continuous development over the centuries, and was formed in the consciousness of our people based on noble concepts such as freedom, independence, Motherland, kindness, and honor. Spirituality is absorbed into a person along with mother's milk, father's example, ancestors' fertilizer. Proximity to nature, enjoying the unspoiled beauty of the beloved country nourishes and strengthens spirituality. At the same time, it acts as a set of social qualities of a person, which do not pass from parents in a natural way, completely and directly, but arise in the process of his formation as a mature person and education. These qualities are manifested in the material and spiritual activities of a person, in his communication with others, and in his attitude towards society and others. Another aspect is that spirituality acts as a unique social phenomenon that covers the entire diversity of a person's way of life and activity, material and cultural needs, his thinking, worldview, moral image, creativity.

Thousands of years of our history testify that nobility and humanity, striving for interethnic harmony are among the highest qualities of our people. Traditions in this regard are passed down from generation to generation. Article 8 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan clearly states that "the people of Uzbekistan are made up of citizens, regardless of their nationality"¹. The concept of "People of Uzbekistan" serves as a moral basis for mutual respect, friendship and solidarity between people of different nationalities and ethnic groups living in our country and working towards a common goal. Such an environment does not allow the emergence of various problems in inter-ethnic relations and is of great importance in the implementation of national ideas such as the development of the Motherland, the peace of the country, and the well-being of the people.

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¹ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Adolat, 2023. - p. 7.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

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